

Additions and corrections to the publication “Three new species and one new subspecies of *Euxoa* Hübner, [1821], subgenus *Chorizagrotis* Smith, 1890 (Noctuidae, Agrotina) from Asia (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)”, with the description of a further new species of this subgenus

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Abstract. The first part of this publication (Introduction) is an addition and correction of the former publication of the author on the *Euxoa* Hübner, [1821], subgenus *Chorizagrotis* Smith, 1890 (Noctuidae, Agrotina) this year (Gyulai, 2026), maintaining the validity of the four new taxa described therein, supported by the documentation of the types of two fundamentally important related species acquired in the meantime. The second part provides the diagnosis and description of a new *Euxoa* (*Chorizagrotis*) species, *E. (Ch.) viaserica* sp. n. The main external and genitalia features of the new species and of its closest relative are characterised and discussed. The imagoes are illustrated on two tables with 9 figures, and the genitalia are presented on two monochromatic plates with figures of 3 males and 9 females.

Key words: *Euxoa*, addition and correction, China, Qinghai, new species, description, taxonomy.

Citation. Gyulai P. 2026: Additions and corrections to the publication “Three new species and one new subspecies of *Euxoa* Hübner, [1821], subgenus *Chorizagrotis* Smith, 1890 (Noctuidae, Agrotina) from Asia (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)”, with the description of a further new species of this subgenus. – *Lepidopterologica Hungarica* 22: 89–95.

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Introduction

With reference to the recently published PDF version of “Three new species and one new subspecies of *Euxoa* Hübner, [1821], subgenus *Chorizagrotis* Smith, 1890 (Noctuidae, Agrotina) from Asia (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)” (Gyulai P. 2026, *Lepidopterologica Hungarica* 22: 19–28), the Editor-in-Chief of the journal received a written communication noting that, although the validity of the four newly described taxa is not in question, certain inaccuracies were identified in the figures depicting the females of *Euxoa* (*Chorizagrotis*) *inexpectata* (Alphéraky, 1897).

Following a detailed examination of the published illustrations, the relevant literature, the available genitalia preparations, and the type material of *Euxoa* (*Chorizagrotis*) *adumbrata* (Eversmann, 1842) (Figs 1, 10 in the present paper) and *Euxoa* (*Chorizagrotis*) *inexpectata* (Figs 7, 17 herein), kindly provided by Alexey Yu. Matov (Russian Academy of Sciences, Zoological Institute of RAS, Saint Petersburg, Russia), it became necessary to issue the following statement and corrigendum.

The four taxa described in the original publication are undoubtedly new, a conclusion not disputed by the author of the aforementioned comment; indeed, some of these taxa had already been suspected to represent species nova in Plante I. (Aulombard et al. 2020). The figures of the male adults and the male genitalia are accurate and reliable. Potential issues arise, however, in the interpretation of certain female genitalia attributed to *E. (Ch.) inexpectata*, namely preparations GYP 2730 (Fig. 22; corresponding to adult no. 9), GYP 6299 (Fig. 21; adult no. 8), and GYP 6298 (Fig. 23; without associated adult illustration).

Of these, specimen GYP 6299 (Fig. 21) clearly requires correction, as it represents a female of *Euxoa rossica* (Staudinger, 1881), based on genital morphology, despite the somewhat shorter-than-usual sclerotised plates in the ductus bursae. This misidentification does not affect the validity of the newly described species, even if the specimen is indeed referable to *E. rossica*, as the length of the ductal plates and their connection to the antrum are known to be variable.

It should also be taken into account that in Central and Inner Asia, *E. adumbrata*, *E. inexpectata*, and *E. rossica* occur sympatrically and are often on the wing simultaneously. Adults of all three species exhibit considerable variation in habitus and colouration, while the genital structures of both sexes show only minor interspecific differences. Consequently, hybrid individuals or atypical forms are likely to occur with some regularity.

This is exemplified by specimens GYP 2730 (Fig. 22) and GYP 6298 (Fig. 23), whose female genitalia show affinities to *E. rossica*, yet deviate from the typical condition, particularly in the reduced sclerotisation of the ductal plates. A comparable case was illustrated by Michael Fibiger (1997), who figured an unusual male specimen from Mongolia (Adz Bogd Uul; Noctuidae Europaeae, vol. 3: 35, fig. 4), exhibiting a mosaic of characters: the slightly larger left side corresponding to *E. (Ch.) inexpectata*, and the slightly smaller right side to *E. (Ch.) adumbrata*. Fibiger considered whether this specimen represented a distinct species, subspecies, or merely an aberrant form, ultimately favouring the latter interpretation.

Similarly, specimen GYP 2730 (Fig. 22) is best interpreted as an aberrant or possibly hybrid individual. This interpretation is supported by the structure of the female genitalia: the ductus bursae plates resemble those of a robust *E. rossica* in their posterior portion, yet originate anteriorly from a short, thickened, truncated base not characteristic of that species.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein include: PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary); GYP = genitalia slide of Péter Gyulai; AM = genitalia slide of Alexey Matov; AV = genitalia slide of Anton Volynkin; RAS = Russian Academy of Sciences, Zoological Institute, Saint-Petersburg, Russia; m = male; f = female; HT = holotype; PT = paratype.

Description of the new species

Euxoa (Chorizagrotis) viasERICA sp. n. (Figs 3, 4, 5, 6, 12, 15, 16)

Holotype: m, China, Prov. Qinghai, Heka Mts., 3720 m, Qing Qeng He, n. river, 4–5.viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai, slide no. GYP 1160, deposited in coll. P. Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary).

Paratypes. 3 males and 5 females, with the same data as the holotype; 1 female, China, Prov. Qinghai, Liu Shao Gou Mt., SE of Kuku Noor (Qinghai) lake, 3580 m, 2–3.viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 1 female, China, Prov. Qinghai, SE Qinghai Mts. range Tawen Mts., S of Kuku–Noor (Qinghai) lake, 3450m, 31.vii. –1. viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM), slides GYP 1206 male; GYP 1250, 6334 females.

Diagnosis. *Euxoa (Chorizagrotis) viasERICA* sp. n. (Figs 3–6) is similar and the most closely related to *E. (Ch.) adumbrata* (Figs 1, 2). *E. (Ch.) viasERICA* sp. n. can be distinguished from *E. (Ch.) adumbrata* by the in average smaller size (29–33 mm and 29–37 mm, respectively), less elongate forewings, lighter, almost concolorous dark brown ground color of the head and thorax vestures and forewings; the total lack of the more or less yellowish filling of the macules and sometimes of the blackish antemedial and postmedial transversal lines (which is more or less present on the *E. (Ch.) adumbrata*) and the much more conspicuous antemedial and postmedial transversal lines.

Description (Figs 3, 4, 5, 6). Wingspan 29–33 mm. Antennae filiform, in males very finely bipectinated. Vesture of the head and thorax, the ground colour of the forewings and the fringe are concolorous brown. The orbicular and reniform macules are typical, the same colour as the ground colour, with fine, not complete blackish encircles; the claviform spot is

hardly discernible. The antemedial line is wavy, the postmedial transversal line arched, densely serrate, and the veins from it toward the outside are covered with fine, darker scales. Subterminal line is dark brown, sinuous and densely serrate, with a fuscous, diffuse shade on the inner side. The terminal line is dark brown, interrupted. Hindwing brownish, with broad, diffuse brownish marginal suffusion and a finely arched, conspicuous cellular macula. The underside of the forewings is whitish with brownish suffusion, almost without the shade of the wing pattern, except the diffuse postmedial line and the reniform stigma; hindwings are whitish with a fine medial line and a broad brownish marginal suffusion.

The male genitalia (Fig.12) are characterised by a weak and long, apically pointed uncus; the subquadrangular juxta, dorsally–medially with a u-shaped deep depression with two lateral, triangular, symmetric extensions and with a triangular ventral extension. Valvae are almost evenly elongate and slender, medially slightly curved outwards, with a dorsally elongate cucullus section, terminated in a row of strong setae. The harpe is short, slightly outwards curved and slender, apically rounded. The sacculus processes are strong, long, straight; the vinculum is v-shaped. The aedeagus is strong and somewhat curved ventrally. The everted tube of the endophallus is recurved dorsally, the basal diverticulum large, conical, prominent; the medial one is small, flatly recurved; the tube of the vesica is distally almost evenly broad; the terminal diverticulum is almost absent, flat.

In the female genitalia (Figs 15, 16), the ovipositor is moderately long, terminally slender, and apically rounded. Apophyses anteriores medium long, strong, apophyses posteriores very long, fine, about three times as long as apophyses anteriores. The antrum and the sclerotised dorsal and ventral plates forming v-shape in the end of the ductus bursae; the tip of the ventral sclerotised laminar plate in the wall is finely rounded. Ductus bursae is membranous, tubular, and evenly broadened posteriorly. Appendix bursae basally broad, large, but hardly prominent. The corpus bursae is large, saccate, and the anterior section is asymmetrically saccate, elongated, while the anterior section is much larger, spacious.

Distribution. The new species is known only from the high mountains of the NE part of the Tibetan plateau in the province Qinghai, China.

Etymology. The name of the new species originates from the Latin name of the famous Silk Road (Via Serica), led from China (also through Qinghai) to the west. „Seres“ means the people of the silk, the Chinese, the inhabitants/traders of the Silk Road.

Comment. This species has already been figured in Esperiana 8, plate 31, fig. 13, as *Euxoa* (*Chorizagrotis*) sp., without name.

Acknowledgements. The author is grateful to Alexey Yu. Matov (Russian Academy of Sciences, Zoological Institute, Saint-Petersburg, Russia) for the type documentation of *E. (Ch.) adumbrata* and of *E. (Ch.) inexpectata* and the dissection of the lectotype of *E. (Ch.) adumbrata* and for the review of the manuscript; to Anton V. Volynkin (Altai State University, Russia and African Natural History Research Trust, Street Court, Kingsland, Leominster, England) for the dissection of the holotype of *E. (Ch.) inexpectata*; to Adrienne Gyulai-Garai (Miskolc, Hungary) for computer and microscopic assistance; to Imre Fazekas (Pécs, Hungary) for checking, edit and publish the manuscript. Finally, I would like to thank Peter Gergely (H-Csobánka) for his useful comments.

Figures 1–8. *Euxoa* (*Chorizagrotis*) spp. adults. 1. *E. (Ch.) (=Agrotis) adumbrata* (Eversmann, 1842), lectotype, m, Kazan district, Siberia, Russia, Matov0740 (RAS); 2. *E. (Ch.) adumbrata* (Eversmann, 1842), female, Russia, Siberia, Altai, Akturaj, 2050 m, Chujskij hrebet, 19–20.vii.2002, leg. T. Hác & I. Juhász, GYP 6308 (PGM); 3. *E. (Ch.) viasERICA* sp. n., HT, m, China, Prov. Qinghai, Heka Mts., 3720 m, Qing Qeng He, n. river, 4–5.viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai, slide no. GYP 1160 (PGM); 4. *E. (Ch.) viasERICA* sp. n., PT, m, China, Prov. Qinghai, Heka Mts., 3720 m, Qing Qeng He, n. river, 4–5.viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai, (PGM); 5. *E. (Ch.) viasERICA* sp. n., PT, f, China, Prov. Qinghai, Heka Mts., 3720 m, Qing Qeng He, n. river, 4–5. viii. 1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 6. *E. (Ch.) viasERICA* sp. n., PT, f, China, Prov. Qinghai, Heka Mts., 3720 m, Qing Qeng He, n. river, 4–5.viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai, slide no. GYP 1250 (PGM); 7. *E. (Ch.) inexpectata* (Alphéraky, 1897), HT and labels, f, Russia, Sidemi, AV. 1016 (RAS).

Figures 8–9 *Euxoa* (*Chorizagrotis*) spp. adults and **Figures 10–12**. male genitalia. **8.** *E. (Ch.) inexpectata* (Alphéraky, 1897), f, Kyrgyzstan, Transalai, Aram Kungei, 3000–3200 m, 23.vii.1995, leg. V. A. Lukhtanov, GYP 6332 (PGM); **9.** *E. (Ch.) inexpectata* (Alphéraky, 1897), f., Kyrgyzstan, Transalai, Aram Kungei, 3000–3200m, 20–21.vii.1995, leg. V. A. Lukhtanov, GYP 6333 (PGM); **10.** *E. (Ch.) (=Agrotis) adumbrata* (Eversmann, 1842), lectotype, capsule, Kazan district, Siberia, Russia, Matov 0740 (RAS); **11.** *E. (Ch.) adumbrata* (Eversmann, 1842), aedeagus, Russia, Siberia, Altai, Akturaj, 2050 m, Chujskij hrebet, 19–20.vii.2002, leg. T. Hác & I. Juhász, GYP 6310 (PGM); **12.** *E. (Ch.) viasERICA* sp. n., HT, China, Prov. Qinghai, Heka Mts., 3720 m, Qing Qeng He, n. river, 4–5.viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai, slide no. GYP 1160 (PGM); **13.** *E. (Ch.) inexpectata* (Alphéraky, 1897), Kyrgyzstan, 60 km. N Naryn, Dolon pass, 3030m, vii.1993, leg. A. Saldaitis, GYP 6336 (PGM).

Figures 14–20. *Euxoa* (*Chorizagrotis*) spp. female genitalia. **14.** *E. (Ch.) adumbrata* (Eversmann, 1842), Tajikistan, Pamir Mts., Yuzno–Alichurskiy range, Dzhilongy village, 3500m, 29.vii.–3.viii.2014, leg. D. A. Safronov, GYP 4793 (PGM); **15.** *E. (Ch.) viasERICA* sp. n., PT, China, Prov. Qinghai, Heka Mts., 3720 m, Qing Qeng He, n. river, 4–5. viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai, slide no. GYP 1250 (PGM); **16.** *E. (Ch.) viasERICA* sp. n., PT, China, Prov. Qinghai, Heka Mts., 3720 m, Qing Qeng He, n. river, 4–5.viii.1999, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai, slide no. GYP 6334 (PGM); **17.** *E. (Ch.) inexpectata* (Alphéraky, 1897), HT, Russia, Sidemi, AV. 1016 (RAS). **18.** *E. (Ch.) inexpectata* (Alphéraky, 1897), Kyrgyzstan, Transalai, Aram Kungei, 3000–3200m, 20–21. vii.1995, leg. V. A. Lukhtanov, GYP 6332 (PGM); **19.** *E. (Ch.) inexpectata* (Alphéraky, 1897), Kyrgyzstan, Transalai, Aram Kungei, 3000–3200 m, 20–21.vii.1995, leg. V. A. Lukhtanov, GYP 6333 (PGM); **20.** *E. rossica* Staudinger, 1881, Kyrgyzstan, Dolon pass, 60 km. N Naryn, 3030 m, vii.1993, leg. A. Saldaitis, GYP 6014 (PGM).

References

- Alphéraky S.N. 1897: Lépidoptères. Lépidoptères de l'Amour et de la Corée – in Romanoff, Mémoires sur les lépidoptères **9** : [151](#)–184, pl. [10](#)–13.
- Aulombard F., Landry B., Lopes Curval P., Ronkay G., Ronkay L. & Varga Z. 2020: La collection Jacques Plante de Noctuidae. Première partie. Noctuinae et Hadeninae / The Plante Noctuidae Collection. Part 1. Noctuinae and Hadeninae. In: Landry, B. (ed.). – Mémoires de la Société de physique et d'histoire naturelle de Genève **49** (1): 1–344.
- Eversmann E.F. 1842: Quaedam Lepidopterorum. Species novae, in Rossia Orientali observatae, nunc descriptae et depictae – Bulletin de la Société impériale des naturalistes de Moscou (**3**) : [543](#)–565, pl. [5](#)–6.
- Fibiger M. 1997: Noctuinae III. Noctuidae Europeae 3. – Entomological Press Sorø, 418 pp.
- Gyulai P. & Ronkay L.: The Noctuidae material collected by Péter Gyulai and Adrienne Garai in the Qinghai region, China, in 1999 – *Esperiana* **8**: 655–700.
- Gyulai P. 2026: Three new species and one new subspecies of *Euxoa* Hübner, [1821], subgenus *Chorizagrotis* Smith, 1890 (Noctuidae, Agrotina) from Asia (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). – *Lepidopterologica Hungarica* **22**: 19–28.
- Püngeler R. 1906: Neue palaearktische Macrolepidopteren. – *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift Iris* **19** (2): 78–98.
- Smith J.B. 1890: Contributions to a Monograph of the Insects of the Lepidopterous Family Noctuidae of Temperate North America. Revision of the Species of the Genus *Agrotis*. – *Bulletin of the United States National Museum* **38**: 1–237, 4 plates.
- Staudinger O. 1881: Beitrag zur Lepidopterenfauna Central-Asiens – *Stettiner Entomologische Zeitung* 42 (7–9): 253–300, (10–12): 393–424.